

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15837667

Perception of Basic Science Teachers on the Implementation of Post Basic Science Content in Jalingo Education Zone , Taraba State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated teachers' perception on the adequacy and implementation of the Basic Science curriculum at the post-basic education level in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to: determine teachers' perception of the adequacy of the Basic Science curriculum; ascertain teachers' perception on its implementation; The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population comprised all 273 Basic Science teachers across 52 public secondary schools in the Jalingo Education Zone, covering three local government areas. A census sampling technique was employed, involving the entire population as the study sample. Data were collected using a structured instrument titled Basic Science Curriculum Questionnaire (BSCQ). To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted. The reliability coefficient computed using Cronbach Alpha was 0.78, indicating a high level of internal consistency. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research questions, while the Chi-square goodness-of-fit test was used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to curriculum evaluation and policy enhancement in science education, particularly at the post-basic level in Nigeria. Findings revealed that the extent of adequacy of Basic Science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba is high, The extent of adequacy of instructional materials for Basic Science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba is high. Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made: Government should regularly employ qualified teachers for the schools while replacing those leaving the job promptly and Teachers of basic science should be encouraged to attend seminars and workshops on regular basis to acquire the skills on improvisation of scarce instructional materials and the use of modern methods of teaching.

Keywords: Basic science curriculum, methods of teaching, teachers' perception

INTRODUCTION

Science in its very simple term, is regarded as the attempt by humans to gain better understanding and clearer interpretation of human beings and the environment. Helping to gain better understanding of the world, however, science is put in a better position to influence positive conditions for life on planet. Also, science is an act of inquiry, which includes empirical observation and experimentation. Alebiosu (2013) posits that science aims at searching for causes and providing reasons for or solutions to phenomena or experiences in life. Umeoduagu (2016) equally opines that right from the time of creation human was not only faced with the task of finding explanations to the vagaries of this universe but also, with the task of finding answers to the myriad problems encountered each passing day, in this case science has been a veritable tool. Marx (2018) believes that science has been described as one of the greatest weapons

human has ever invented for leaping into the unknown phenomenon. It has also been described as the language of nature, without which communicating with the world, within or outside becomes impossible. Basic Science that is taught in schools has developed as a process of gradual curriculum reform in science.

Therefore, if a teacher is untrained or unwilling to implement curriculum plans, his or her desired success cannot be attained. Also, there is the need for the teacher to be equipped with appropriate instructional resources. These instructional resources could be in the form of books, charts, models, maps, laboratory materials and equipment, projectors; computers and so on. The book has been regarded as an important single resource to both the science teacher and the learner. Some commentators in education have remarked that if education is the road out of poverty, books are the wheels needed for the journey. Books and other materials that will aid learning must be available and adequately provided in schools. Dike (2016) asserts that if we want children and all citizens to acquire literacy, we must provide reading materials, the abundant and pleasurable reading materials found in libraries. It is expected that once a curriculum is designed, it may be evaluated by internal evaluation, expert appraisal and confidential review.

Testing and implementation of the curriculum should be accompanied by evaluation. Evaluation involves the assessment of activities that occur when the curriculum is implemented in the classroom. The idea of formative, summative and even process evaluation is a pointer to the fact that, evaluation is an on-going process. In the words of Obashoro (2012), evaluation is to assess and place value on: programme objectives and needs; programme input and process; availability and adequacy of resources (human and material); characteristics of participants; teaching and learning methodologies; and programme outcome and impact. Evaluating the implementation of the basic science curriculum will help in ascertaining that the essential elements for the attainment of the programme objective are put in place, thereby putting the programme on a sound footing. The plight of school curriculum implementation in Nigeria has been attributed to many factors including funding, obsolete educational facilities, and inadequate qualified teachers among others. Afuwape and Olatoye (2014) stated that lack of

qualified teachers, lack of equipment and facilities for teaching, lack of practical work in integrated science (basic Science) and poor methods of teaching are the major factors militating against the successive implementation of the core curriculum in Integrated Science (basic Science). Poor teacher qualification is another problem militating against effective implementation of Basic Science curriculum.

The implementation of the basic science programme in secondary schools in Nigeria has been a matter of serious concern to educationist. Researchers (Usman, 2013, Utegbe, 2015) have shown that, the programme is expected to equip students with the necessary basic scientific skills to build progressive society. A good number of students do not go beyond basic education level and those who do, do not offer courses related to science disciplines. Thus, the implementation of the basic science programme is suspected to be faced with a myriad of problems.

Perception of Basic Science teachers' knowledge of subject matter is absolutely depended on the teacher's knowledge and not gender, and knowledge occurs in a variety of forms. Teacher's effectiveness is impeded if the teacher is unfamiliar with the body of knowledge taught. The ability to teach effectively depends on the Basic Science teachers' knowledge and knowledge occurs in a variety of forms. The implication of this for teachers is that they must thoroughly understand the content of what they teach. The teachers who understand the content of topic taught use clearer language, their discourse is more connected, and they provide better explanation than those whose background is weaker irrespective of gender. The study of science is very important especially in today's world of science and technology. This is because it provides solutions to many if not all problems encountered by man on earth. Opinion moulders such as Okoro (2011) have opined that the development of this critical sector holds the key to rapid transformation of any society. The importance of science and technology to national development in the life of any country cannot be over- emphasized. This is because knowledge and skills in science and technology are very vital in the development of any society.

Facilities are plants, equipment, buildings, furniture such as table, chairs which enable workers to perform their work effectively. To Ehiamentalor (2011). Facilities are: “those factors which enable production workers to achieve the goals of an organization.” Olorok (2016) in supporting Ehiamentalor (2011) notes that the use of instructional facilities enhance learning experiences and leads to interaction within the learning environment. Onyeachus (2016) study questions such as “what extent are facilities being provided for effective implementation of secondary education curriculum?” Findings revealed that facilities are not provided adequately. What is found in most secondary schools in Nigeria are dilapidated buildings, leaking roofs, lack of chairs and tables for students and teachers use. These affect students’ performance. Lamenting on the type of building found in our secondary schools, Nwachuku (2015) remarks that, the public sector of education (primary and secondary levels) has witnessed stagnation and decay.

The persistent poor performance in science especially Basic Science among students makes it imperative to evaluate the post basic science curriculum programme to find out the reason for their poor performance. The new curriculum addresses issues of value re – orientation, poverty eradication, critical thinking, entrepreneurship and life skills, in spite of these concerted efforts at ensuring an effective transformation of education system. The implementation is lacking, or the process is very slow at the speed of snail’s movement. Going by research evidence on poor performance in science by students reasons abound such as teachers shy away from teaching science practically. The teachers often complain of inadequate or lack of science instructional materials to justify the use of expository method. Meanwhile, there are readily available resources within the local environment which can be used for the teaching of Basic Science concepts. However, many teachers shy away from using them even when they may be available.

The implementation of basic science in Taraba State, Nigeria is suspected to be faced with a myriad of problems (Utegbe, 2014). Despite efforts made by government to use this programme to attain technological advancement of the country, this does not seem to have yielded positive desired. Therefore the researcher deemed it fit to investigate teachers perception on the adequacy and implementation of post Basic Science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state, Nigeria.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate teachers perception on the adequacy and implementation of post Basic Science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to: ‘

- i. Determine teachers’ perception on the adequacy of Basic Science curriculum of post basic education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State Nigeria
- ii. Ascertain teachers’ perception on the implementation of the Basic Science curriculum at post basic education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State Nigeria

Research Questions

The following questions are formulated to guide the study

- i. To what extent do Basic Science teachers perceive the adequacy of Basic Science curriculum of Basic education?
- ii. To what extent do Basic Science teachers perceive the implementation of Basic Science curriculum in teaching of Post Basic education in Jalingo Education Zone?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are proposed for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of teachers’ perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone.

H₀₂ There is no significant impact of teachers’ perception on the implementation of Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of this study comprises of all the Basic Science teachers from the 52 public secondary schools in the Jalingo education zone of Taraba state 273 Basic Science teachers across the Zone. The sample for the study comprises the entire population of 273 Basic Science teachers from 52 public secondary schools in the three local government areas in Jalingo education zone of Taraba state. The Instrument for data collection is questionnaire titled: Basic Science Curriculum Questionnaire (BSCQ). In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, pilot test was carried out to pre-test the research instruments. The BSCQ was trial tested at Government Day Secondary School Mai-Hula and Government Day Secondary School Bali all in Bali education zone, which are not part of the target population of the study. The schools to be used are outside the area of the study, but have some degree of similarities with sampled schools Results obtained from the pilot study was used to compute the reliability of instrument using Cronbach Alpha. This is suitable for determining the internal consistency or average correlation of items in a survey instrument (Emaikwu, 2011). The reliability coefficient obtained is 0.78 and the instrument is considered reliable . The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic of chi-square. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while the chi-square goodness of fit was used to test the Null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Research Question one: *To what extent do Basic Science teachers perceive the adequacy of Basic Science curriculum of Basic education?*

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviations Ratings on the perception of teachers on adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	the content of Basic Science curriculum at post Basic Education is activity-based.	2.33	1.06	D
2.	Cognitive ideas in the content of Basic Science curriculum at post basic Education are practicalized.	2.66	0.78	A
3.	The Instructional aids content Basic Science curriculum at post Basic Education expose learners to issues within their environment.	3.04	0.53	A
4.	The contents of Basic Science curriculum at post Basic Education present topics in a manner that the learners are eager to learn.	3.13	0.59	A
5.	The contents of Basic Science curriculum at Post Basic Education is adequate for teaching.	3.21	0.60	A
6.	There is adequate content of Basic Science curriculum at Post Basic Education.	3.05	0.70	A
7.	The contents of Basic Science curriculum teaching technique at Post Basic Education are emphasized during teaching.	2.60	0.85	A
8.	The Instructional contents of Basic Science curriculum at Post Basic Education provides adequate skills to scientific problems in the society.	2.54	0.80	A
9.	The contents of Basic Science curriculum at Post Basic Education were selected from the environment of the learner.	2.64	0.79	A
10.	The contents of Basic Science curriculum at Post Basic Education provides solution to social challenges in the society.	2.99	0.65	A
	Grand Mean	2.88	0.31	HE

Source: Field Report 2021 Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50 \Rightarrow HE$; $X < 2.50 \Rightarrow LE$

Results in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation scores of the rating items on perception of teachers on adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content in in Jalingo education Zone Taraba State. The results Reveals that only item 1 had low extent adequacy of Instructional material Content. The rest of the items have mean rating scale above 2.50 indicating high extent of adequacy of Instructional material content in Taraba state. The grand mean of 2.88 indicates an overall high extent of adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content in in Jalingo education Zone Taraba state. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion.

Research Question two; *What is the mean perception of male and female Basic Science teachers on the adequacy of Basic Science curriculum of Basic education in Jalingo Education Zone?*

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviations Ratings on perception of male and female Basic Science teachers on the adequacy of Basic Science curriculum of Post Basic education in Jalingo Education Zone

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Rem
1.	There are adequate Chalk boards for the teaching and learning in this school	2.65	0.85	A
2.	There are enough chalks that enable effective teaching in this school	2.82	0.81	A
3.	There are available ICT resources to stimulate students learning	2.35	0.83	A
4.	There are adequate teachers text book in core subjects for effective teaching	2.47	0.87	D
5.	There are adequate text book in core subjects for pupils to read	2.41	0.89	D
6.	There are adequate instructional materials for effective teaching and learning	2.39	0.86	D
7.	There are enough number of classroom in this school	2.17	0.85	D
8.	There are adequate improvised teaching aids this school	2.35	0.83	D
9.	Every teacher is given exercise book for lesson plan/note.	2.47	0.87	D
10.	There is light always in this school.	2.41	0.89	D
Grand Mean		2.31	0.21	LE

Source: Field Report 2021 Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50 \Rightarrow HE$; $X < 2.50 \Rightarrow LE$

Results of Table 2 show the mean and standard deviation scores of the rating items on the adequacy of instructional material for effective implementation of post Basic science curriculum. The results show that only two items (number 1 and 2) shows high extent of adequacy of instructional material for effective implementation of post Basic science curriculum. The rest of the items have mean rating scale below 2.50 indicating low extent of adequacy of instructional material for effective implementation of post Basic science curriculum. The grand mean (2.31) shows a low extent of adequacy of instructional material for effective implementation of post Basic science curriculum. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion.

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone.

Table 3. Chi-square test on impact of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone

Total scores of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone	
Chi-square	239.227 ^a
Df	9
Assymp. sig	0.000

From Table 3, chi-square at 9 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 239.227, p = .000$) signifies that there is significant impact of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone. State is not retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of teacher's perception on the implementation of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone.

Table 4. Chi-Square Test on significant impact of teacher's perception on the implementation of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone

Total scores of teacher's perception on the implementation of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone	
Chi-square	97.273 ^a
Df	8
Assymp. sig	0.000

From Table 6, chi-square at 4 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 97.273, p = .000$) signifies that There is significant impact of teacher's perception on the implementation of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of teacher's perception on the implementation of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone is not retained. Rejecting the null hypothesis that the perception base on gender differ in the usage of Basic Science curriculum at post basic education in Jalingo Education Zone.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Mean and Standard Deviations Ratings on perception of teachers on adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content. The results reveal that only item 1 had low extent adequacy of Instructional material Content. The rest of the items have mean rating scale above 2.50 indicating high extent of adequacy of Instructional material content in Taraba state. The grand mean of (2.88) indicates an overall high extent of adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content in Taraba state. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion it is also evidenced From Table 5, chi-square at 9 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 239.227, p = .000$) signifies that there is significant impact of teacher's perception on the adequacy of Post Basic science curriculum content in Jalingo Education Zone.

The findings of present study contradict the findings of Bamidele and Faremi (2012) on the challenges facing the implementation of Basic Science in Imo State. The results of the study revealed that 65.83 % of the teachers were of the opinion that the Basic Science curriculum content was not activity-oriented and lacked practicalised coefficient ideas. This empirical is related to current study in the sense that the study investigated the adequacy of the Basic Science curriculum content.

Finding on the extent of teachers on usage of Basic Science Curriculum content in Taraba State finding reveals there is an overall high extent of teachers' usage of Basic Science Curriculum content in Taraba State. This is in agreement with the work of Mohammed (2012) conducted a study on primary school teachers' perception of Universal Basic Education curriculum in Kano State. Result revealed that teacher's significantly perceived Basic Science curriculum as not adequately responding to the needs of their pupils. The findings on the perception of teachers on usage of Basic Science Curriculum content in Taraba State findings reveals shows an overall high extent of teachers usage of Basic Science Curriculum content in Taraba State. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion. This is in conformity with lfeakor and Okoli (2013) on the appraisal of the availability and utilization of the Basic Science

curriculum in Imo State. Among the findings, it was revealed that Post Basic Education teachers significantly use the Basic Science curriculum in teaching their classes.

Finding on the adequacy of instructional material for effective implementation of post Basic science curriculum finding reveals the standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion. The findings is in agreement with the work of Mahmuda, (2014) who assessed the implementation of Basic Science programme in Junior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa West Zone of Nasarawa State. The result of the study revealed that Basic Science programmes in Nasarawa West Junior Secondary Schools are being implemented to a large extent, facilities available for the implementation of Basic Science Programmes are not adequate and there is a significant different between the mean perception of rural and urban teachers on the extent of the implementation of the Basic Science programme curriculum in Nasarawa West zone.

The findings is similar to what Ojimba (2013) found out when Investigated if science teachers' perception still requires reforms in spite of the numerous reforms in the educational sector at UBE and secondary school levels. Findings revealed that the teachers perceived inadequacies of previous curriculum as being instrumental to numerous curriculum reforms among other factors.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that the from the findings of the evaluative study of the implementation of the Basic Science curriculum in junior secondary schools, the following conclusions was drawn in Jalingo education zone Taraba State, Nigeria. The results reveal that only item 1 had low extent adequacy of Instructional material Content. The rest of the items have mean rating scale above 2.50 indicating high extent of adequacy of Instructional material content in Taraba state. The grand mean of (2.88) indicates an overall high extent of adequacy of Basic Science Curriculum Instructional material content in Taraba state. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents are not too far from each other in opinion it is concluded that most basic science teachers in secondary schools in Taraba State were qualified to teach Basic science but some of the challenges of creativity in a basic science classroom in the zone were usage of Basic science curriculum content is also accurate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should regularly employ qualified teachers for the schools while replacing those leaving the job promptly.
2. Teachers should motivate the students the more in science subjects and help them see the benefits of science.

REFERENCES

- Aboho, D. A. (_2017). Curriculum innovation and change. Makurdi: Destiny Ventures.
- Ada, N. A. (2015). Essentials of thesis writing. ' A guide to research for students in tertiary institutions. Makurdi: Almond Publishers.
- Adejoh. M. J. (2016). Evaluation of the Integrated Science and Introductory Technology programme in junior secondary schools in Benue State. An unpublished-Ph.D thesis, University of Jos.
- Adeniyi, E. O. (2014). Keynote address delivered at the Nigerian Educational. Research and Development Council organized for National Curriculum Revision and Development Project for Junior Secondary School, 21-28 November, Minna. Niger State.
- Adeniyi, O. (2019). Stimulating values education through National Curriculum and Book Development Effort. In M.O Iwovi, (Ed.). Education for value pp 349-359. Lagos: Foremost Publishers Limited.

- Agbo, A. (2018). Students perceived difficulties in the content of secondary one Biology syllabus. Unpublished M. Ed thesis, University of Jos.
- Ajagun, G. A. (2016). Towards good performance in science education. *Nigerian Journal of Teacher Education & Teaching* 2(1), 117- 125.
- Ajibola, M. A. (2018); Innovation and curriculum development for basic education in Nigeria: Policy priority and challenges of practice and implementation. *Research Journal of International Studies* Issue, 8, 51-58.
- Akpan. B. B. (2018). Nigeria." the future of science education. Ibadan: Oluseyi Press Limited
- Ausubel, (1968). *Educational psychology: A cognitive view*. New York: Holt Rinehart and Advancement of Curriculum Studies, 9, 1-11 .
- Bruner, J. S. (1966). *Towards a theory of instruction*. Cambridge: Havard University Press.
- Chukwunke, B. U., & Nwachukwu, C.O. (2015). State and future education in Nigeria. In J.O. Afe & G.C. Edozie (Eds.), *Book of abstracts and lead papers*. Asaba, Nigeria: West and Solomon Publishing Company. .
- Etiubon, R. U., & Udofia, T. M. (2019). Promoting and sustaining educational ,research for self-reliance. *International Journal of Education Research and Administration*, 6(1), 20 — 26.
- Ezeliora, B. (2014). Perception of science among Nigerian school leavers. Unpublished article for Gender and Science and Technology, South Africa.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2017). *Distribution of Nigerian population* Abuja: Government Press.
- Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development (2016). *National gender policy*. Kaduna: Amana Printing Limited.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National policy on education*. Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2018). *National policy on education*. Lagos: Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) Press.
- Ifeakor, A. C., & Okoli, J.N.. (2013). Appraisal of the availability and utilization of UBE curriculum in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Curriculum and Teaching*, 4(2), 31-36.
- Israel, J. A. (2015). Case of students' low enrolment in Chemistry. *Journal of Empirical Research in Science and Technology Education*, 1(1), 8-12.
- Marsh, C. J., & Willis, G. (2013). *Curriculum alternative approaches."* Ongoing issues (3rd ed.). Post Saddle River N.J.: Merrill Prentice Hall. '
- Martin, R. (2019). *Teaching science for all children (with my education laboratory)*. London: Pearson Education Inc.
- Mulemwa, J.N. (2015). The challenges of providing quality school science in Africa. In M.A.G. Akale (Ed.), *43rd Annual conference proceedings of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria on science, technology and mathematics education for sustainable development in Africa*. Ibadan: Heinemann.
- Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (2017). *9-year basic education curriculum, Mathematics for Post Basic Education JSS 1-3*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Obioma, G. (2016). The role of teachers in the implementation of UBE in Nigeria. Paper presented at the 47th annual conference of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria in Calabar, August 13th - 19th. .
- Obioma, G. (2018). Curriculum implementations and assessment in the 9-year basic education program in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Assessment in Africa*, 2(1), 22-26.
- Ojimba, D. P. (2013). Science education reforms in Nigeria. Implications for science teachers: Global advanced research. *Journal o_/Peace, Gender and Development Studies*, 2(5), 86-90.
- Oke, M. (2012). Gender gap and access to secondary school science education: The way forward. *WAEC Monthly Seminar Paper*, 2, 103-113.
- Okoro, C.O. (2019). *Fundamentals of curriculum development*. Lagos: Cape Publisliers International Limited.

- Okoro, C. (2011). Science Technology and Mathematics (STM) and teacher education: Improving teacher education in the 21st century in Nigeria. Challenges and strategies, Lagos: Gilbert Grace and Gabriel Associates.
- Olawoye, F. A.& Salman, M. F. (2018). Education reforms in Nigeria; Implications for the education of the girl-child, Being a paper presented at the 45th Annual National Conference of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), held in Gusau Girls' Technical advance Teachers' College, Zamfara State, 25th -29th August, 2018.
- Onyedrian, A. M. (2013). Using improvised materials to enhance the teaching of Basic Science in primary schools. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria, 52nd annual conference proceedings.
- Ozaji, B. E. (2018). Effective classroom practices in the teaching and learning of Integrated Science in Jos North Jalingo Education Zone of Plateau State. An unpublished M.Ed thesis, University of Jos.
- Rogers, A. C. (2013). The Tyler-Taba rationales. Journal of the American Association for the
- Salman, M. F (2011). An investigation into female enrolment in mathematics and sciences at the University of Ilorin. Nigerian Journal of Health, Education and Welfare of Special People, 5(1), 65-76.
- Taba, H. (1962). Curriculum development: Theory and practice. New York: Harcourt, Brace and World.
- Tahir, G. (2015). School library development for the Universal Basic Education program. Keynote address presented at the opening ceremony of the 18th Annual Conference of Nigerian School Library Association, 28th October – 1st November.
- Utulu, R.E. (2013) The curriculum and the teacher: Theory and practice. Makurdi: Selfers Publishers.
- Yahaya. L. A (2014). Disparity in the enrolment of male and female undergraduates in science and technology based faculties at the University of Ilorin: Implications for counseling. Nigerian Journal Of C0unseZing and Applied Psychology.